

Comparative Study on Potentiation of Analgesic Activity of Tramadol by Amlodipine and Cilnidipine in Rat Model

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Abstract:

Cilnidipine blocks both L-type and N-type calcium channels and some DHPs can block other subtypes of calcium channels (N, P/Q, R types) and also suggests that DHPs are no longer considered specific L-type blockers. Antinociception was found to be due to the blockade of voltage-gated calcium channels. The study was conducted by using Wistar male albino rats weighing 150–200 grams in good health. The animals were divided into four groups, each group containing six rats, Group I: Control (normal saline), Group II: Tramadol (10mg /Kg), Group III: Tramadol (10mg /Kg) +Amlodipine (5mg/Kg), and Group IV: Tramadol (10mg /Kg) +Cilnidipine (1mg/Kg). Tail flick and hot plate methods were used to evaluate the analgesic effects where group IV had better analgesic effects when compared to the other 3 groups. Hence, Cilnidipine can be preferred in elderly patients who are suffering from hypertension along with neuropathic pain, which can reduce multidrug exposure and increase patient compliance.

Keywords: Pharmacology, Cilnidipine, Amlodipine, Analgesic, antihypertensive.

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Introduction

Current management of fever, pain, and inflammatory diseases is limited to the use of nonsteroidal and steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs whose chronic administration is associated with several adverse effects [1]. Tramadol hydrochloride, a centrally acting analgesic, is a synthetic codeine analog. It acts as μ -opioid receptor agonist and has lower side effects in comparison to typical opioid agents [2]. Tramadol is as effective as morphine or pethidine in the treatment of mild to moderate pain but is less effective in severe or chronic pain. Amlodipine, a

dihydropyridine (DHP) type calcium channel blocker used in hypertension and angina, shows benefits by acting on L-type calcium channels. Further studies revealed that amlodipine blocks voltage-gated calcium channel results in Antinociception [3]. Amlodipine is a dihydropyridine molecule that exhibits a low incidence of tachycardia. This suggests that, in comparison to other members of the DHP family, Amlodipine has relatively little ability to excite the sympathetic nervous system. Thus far, the drug's exceptionally sluggish pharmacokinetic

characteristics have been used to explain its peculiar action. Nonetheless, some research indicates that amlodipine might modulate the neurohormonal system [3]. Amlodipine may potentially have an impact on N-type Ca²⁺ channels, even though it is commonly known that DHPs specifically inhibit L-type Ca²⁺ channels. In nerve and secretory cells, N-type.

Ca²⁺ channel activity is associated with catecholamine release and sympathetic nerve tone. Amlodipine may interact with the N-type Ca²⁺ channel, affecting the neurohormonal and sympathetic nervous systems. To verify this notion, we looked at how nifedipine and amlodipine blocked cloned L-type and N-type Ca²⁺ channels generated in *Xenopus* oocytes. The results clearly show that amlodipine effectively blocks the N-type and L-type Ca²⁺ channels. N-Type calcium channels are found primarily at presynaptic terminals and are involved in neurotransmission [4]. The inhibitory effect on the N-type Ca²⁺ channel by Cilnidipine may bestow an additional clinical advantage for the treatment of hypertension, such as suppression of reflex tachycardia. L- and N-type Ca²⁺ channel blocker cilnidipine reduce neuronal damage in the rat brain. [5]

Codeine analogues that are synthetic consist of tramadol hydrochloride, which is a centrally acting analgesic. By exerting its properties as an ϵ -opioid receptor agonist, it inhibits the reabsorption of serotonin and norepinephrine, leading to monoaminergic spinal suppression of pain. Its negative effects are milder than those of conventional opioid drugs. For mild to moderate pain, tramadol works as well as morphine or pethidine; however, it is less effective in treating severe or chronic pain. Amlodipine affects L-type calcium channels, which is beneficial. It is a dihydropyridine (DHP) type calcium channel blocker used in hypertension and angina pectoris. Further studies have shown that cilnidipine and amlodipine also block N-type calcium channels.

This finding suggests that some DHPs can block other subtypes of calcium channels (N, P/Q, R types) and also suggests that DHPs are no longer considered specific L-type blockers. Antinociception was found to be due to blockade of voltage-gated calcium channels. The distribution of non-L-type calcium channels is different in both the central and peripheral nervous systems.

N-type calcium channels are important in neurotransmission and are mostly located in presynaptic terminals. These channels open in response to the strong depolarization caused by the action potential, allowing calcium influx and vesicle fusion, which releases stored neurotransmitters.

Drugs and endogenous chemical transmitters can block N-type and L-type calcium channels to terminate nociceptive signaling. However, the pharmacological properties of DHP affect everyone. Amlodipine exerted an antinociceptive effect at high doses. Low-dose amlodipine potentiated the antinociceptive effects of the sub analgesic ketorolac but not tramadol. At moderate and higher dose, amlodipine significantly increases the antinociceptive effect of both peripherally acting ketorolac and centrally acting tramadol [6].

The third-generation CCB amlodipine has a better pharmacological profile. The primary side effect of amlodipine is pedal swelling. Some clinical studies have shown that amlodipine increases endothelial nitric oxide release and decreases atrial nitric oxide release (ANP). Long-term amlodipine treatment also increases the release of catecholamines from sympathetic nerve endings. Cilnidipine reduces proteinuria in the kidney by relaxing both afferent and efferent. Although many studies are available on amlodipine and cilnidipine treatment, no specific studies are comparing electrocardiographic changes, and echocardiographic and biochemical parameters between groups [7]. Cilnidipine found superior to amlodipine for reducing systolic BP and equally efficacious in reducing DBP. However, these need to be further proved in other animal models and in clinical studies.

Study Plan:

Methods

The study was conducted by using Wistar male albino rats weighing 150–200 grams in good health. The animals were stored in cages within the departmental animal house with temperature-controlled rooms with air conditioning, and in typical laboratory settings with a 12-hour light and dark cycle as per the guidelines. They were fed regular animal feed and had unlimited access to water. The animals were kept for accommodation for 7 days. The experimental protocol was accepted by the institutional animal ethics committee. The animals were divided into four groups, each group contains six rats.

- Group I: Control (normal saline).
- Group II: Tramadol (10mg /Kg).
- Group III: Tramadol (10mg /Kg)+Amlodipine (5mg/Kg)
- Group IV: Tramadol (10mg /Kg)+Cilnidipine (1mg/Kg)
- Tramadol to be administered intra peritoneally; Amlodipine and Cilnidipine to be administered orally after preparing fresh solutions.
- Determination of analgesic activity

Drugs:

Amlodipine besylate from Micro labs, Cilnidipine from lupins pharma, Tramadol from Dr. Reddy's

Laboratories received through Vinayaga pharmacy Aarupadai Veedu Medical College & Hospital Puducherry using instruments: Analgesiometer – tail flick and Hot plate

Tail flick method

Antinociceptive activity was measured by tail flick method using analgesiometer. Radiant heat from an electric source was used as a stimulus and the time required for the sudden flicking of the tail was considered as the 'reaction time' or 'the tail flick latency' (TFL).

The baseline reaction time is to be obtained at the start of experiment (0 hrs) just before the drug

administration. In case of the groups in which only control (saline), and tramadol, TFL test was repeated at 15, 30, 60, 90 mins and 2 hrs. After the administration of the drugs.

In the groups receiving combined treatment, the two drugs were administered at different times. After observing baseline (0 hrs) reaction time at the start of experiment amlodipine was administered.

Tramadol was given 5 hrs after the administration of amlodipine and then repeat test at 6, 6.25, 6.5, 7, 7.5, and 8 hrs (0, 15, 30, 60, 90 mins and 2 hrs) from baseline. Similarly, tramadol was given 2 hrs after the administration of cilnidipine.

Figure 1: Tail flick method

Hot Plate Test

The rats was kept on a hot plate maintained at 55°C within the restrainer. The reaction time (in seconds) or latency period was determined as the time taken for the rats to react to the thermal pain by licking their paws or jumping. The reaction time was recorded before (0min) and at 15, 30, 60, 90 mins

and 2 hrs. after the administration of the treatments. The maximum reaction time has been fixed at 45 sec to prevent any injury to the tissues of the paws.

If the reading exceeds 45 sec, it would be considered as maximum analgesia. The maximum possible analgesia (MPA) was calculated with standard formula.

Figure 2: Hot plate method

Statistical Analysis: One way ANOVA with post hoc test of significance was performed for comparison amongst different means. P < 0.05 will be regarded as statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Groups of animals given various drugs

Group of animals	Drug	Dose
I	Normal saline	1.5ml/kg
II	Tramadol	10mg/kg
III	Tramadol +Amlodipine	10mg/kg + 5mg/kg
IV	Tramadol + Cilnidipine	10mg/kg + 1mg/kg

Figure 3: Tail Flick method of Group 1 (control), showing noticeable fluctuation at 30 minutes, with an increase in 2 and 5 observations

Figure 4: Tail flick method of test groups, where Group 4 shows a sharp increase in values, followed by a continued rise over the next two hours, suggesting a comparable response pattern over time

Figure 5: Hot plate method of Group 1 (control) shows a minor decrease by 15 minutes, followed by a slight rise at 90 minutes and stabilizes at 2 hours

Table 2: Hot plate method, where Group 4 shows a sharp rise by 15 minutes along with a slight decrease is observed at 2 hours, indicating a secondary peak followed by stabilization

Time	group2						group-3						group-4					
	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	3	4	5	6
0 mins	29.56	30.3	26.54	30.25	30.14	30.23	31.45	30.25	30.45	31.85	31.23	31.48	29.56	30.25	29.58	29.54	28.64	31.45
15 Mins	37.65	38.49	37.45	37.15	38.64	39.54	36.54	38.65	36.48	38.45	38.71	37.64	38.57	39.57	38.65	39.54	40.65	39.74
30 mins	40.65	40.65	41.25	41.65	40.94	42.94	40.65	40.95	39.12	39.46	40.64	40.85	41.85	41.34	41.14	41.64	41.22	43.45

60 min s	40.95	41.54	41.84	41.65	41.27	40.85	40.34	40.26	40.75	41.35	40.26	40.68	41.45	42.34	42.84	42.34	42.72	41.24
90 Min s	42.65	43.67	41.26	45.67	40.97	46.24	41.92	43.64	41.37	45.64	40.24	46.34	43.64	44.75	42.54	46.57	41.35	47.95
2 hrs	40.95	37.54	39.57	46.25	47.87	45.67	40.24	37.24	40.67	45.24	47.95	45.34	41.29	39.65	41.24	46.78	48.14	46.95

Table 3: Tail flick method, ANOVA between four groups. From 15 minutes onward the p value is 0.00001 at each time point, indicating highly significant differences between groups ($p < 0.05$)

Time	Groups				P value
	1	2	3	4	
0 min	4.1933±0.0848	4.4±0.1971	4.3433±0.2767	4.56±0.2431	0.053
15 mins	4.2467±0.1242	4.6133±0.1382	18.1017±0.5532	19.3567±0.1726	0.00001
30 mins	4.2683±0.127	4.725±0.0973	19.2633±0.4789	21.4833±0.2053	0.00001
60 mins	29.7283±0.3979	41.35±0.3956	40.6067±0.4219	42.1483±0.66	0.00001
90 mins	4.2367±0.0734	4.6817±0.1938	20.3683±0.1652	22.0233±0.6013	0.00001
2 hrs	4.2267±0.0776	4.7817±0.1497	22.4283±0.2812	22.975±0.5334	0.00001

Table 4 Hot plate method, from 15 minutes onward the p value is 0.00001, showing statistically significant differences between groups ($p < 0.05$)

Time	Groups				P value
	1	2	3	4	
0 min	30.4283±0.685	29.5033±1.4772	29.8367±0.9419	31.1183±0.6308	0.051
15 mins	30.2±0.3854	38.1533±0.8975	39.4533±0.7695	37.745±1.0306	0.00001
30 mins	29.875±0.8156	41.3467±0.869	41.7733±0.8637	40.2783±0.7821	0.00001
60 mins	29.7283±0.3979	41.35±0.3956	42.155±0.662	40.6067±0.4219	0.00001
90 mins	30.155±0.9282	43.41±2.2063	44.4667±2.4798	43.1917±2.4395	0.00001
2 hrs	30.2067±0.4624	42.975±4.1757	44.0083±3.673	42.78±4.0232	0.00001

Discussion

Hypertension is a significant global health concern due to its widespread prevalence. In India, the prevalence is estimated at 24%–30% in urban areas and 12%–14% in rural regions. Globally, hypertension is responsible for 13.5% of premature deaths, 54% of stroke cases, and 47% of ischemic heart disease cases. By 2025, it is projected that 1.56 billion adults will be affected by high blood pressure. In the Southeast Asia Region, chronic noncommunicable diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, with high blood pressure as a key risk factor, are on the rise. Deaths attributed to these conditions are expected to reach 12.5 million by 2030 [8].

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic inflammatory disease that primarily targets synovial joints, leading to tissue damage. It is commonly manifested in middle-aged individuals. It can also impact extra-articular tissues such as the heart and kidneys. Charles-Schoeman highlighted an increased prevalence of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) in individuals with RA. Similarly, Chung et al observed that hypertension was more prevalent among RA patients compared to control groups. Additionally, Dessein et al noted that hypertension in RA patients might serve as a

traditional cardiovascular risk factor, with its prevalence and characteristics influenced by the presence of the disease [9]. Our study is highly focused on the selection of antihypertensive drugs in hypertensives associated with arthritis which will favor adjuvant analgesic activity.

Our study observed a minor fluctuation in the tail flick method, with no significant changes between the groups. A previous study conducted using mice with Tramadol at 10 mg/kg showed no significant effect on tail-flick latency over 2 hours. However, doses of 22.8 mg/kg (ED50) and 50 mg/kg (ED90) significantly increased reaction time in a dose-dependent manner, with maximum antinociceptive effect observed at 0.5 hours and sustained throughout the test period. They have concluded that tramadol's dose-dependent antinociceptive activity [10].

In this study, L-type calcium channel blockers (CCBs) primarily affect vascular smooth muscle and skeletal muscle, offering indirect pain relief. Improving blood flow and reducing vascular constriction may help conditions like migraines or ischemic pain. Additionally, they may alleviate muscle spasms associated with conditions like tension headaches or myofascial pain. Preclinical studies also suggest that L-type CCBs have

neuroprotective effects, potentially benefiting neuropathic pain. However, their role in pain management is less significant than N-type blockers, with L-type blockers generally not being first-line treatments for chronic pain. At a dose of 3.5 mg/kg, amlodipine increases tail flick latency, consistent with studies showing its intrathecal administration reduces licking in the formalin test's second phase. Similarly, N-type calcium channel blockers like cilnidipine and ω -conotoxin display notable analgesic effects. This may result from calcium channel blockade, which inhibits nociceptive synaptic transmission. Analgesic activity is also observed with N-type calcium channel blockers applied to the subarachnoid space, suggesting their antinociceptive effects arise from this mechanism⁶. In our study with 5mg/kg of Amlodipine with 10mg/kg of Tramadol shows better result when compared to the Tramadol 10mg/kg and control group.

Murakami M et al, conducted a study and observed that Cilnidipine shows strong antinociceptive effects in mice by inhibiting N-type calcium channels in rat DRG neurons [11]. Given the high expression of the N-type subunit in DRG, it likely reduces Ca^{2+} influx and suppresses neurotransmitter release to exert its analgesic action. In our study, on doing tail flick and hot plate method we have observed that Cilnidipine 1mg/kg with Tramadol 10mg/kg shows a significant change ($p < 0.05$) in the analgesic activity when compared to the other three groups.

This study used Amlodipine 5mg/kg along with Tramadol 10mg/kg which showed significant results compared to Tramadol 10mg/kg alone and control groups, and this result was correlated with Modi H et al. In their study, they observed that amlodipine enhanced antinociceptive effects, likely due to its N-type calcium channel blocking action. N-type calcium channel blockers have shown potential as analgesics, particularly when administered into the subarachnoid space. This suggests that amlodipine's antinociceptive effect is primarily mediated through N-type calcium channel inhibition [12].

A study conducted by Yamashita T et al. concluded that cilnidipine is a potential therapeutic agent targeting P2X7 receptors (P2X7Rs) in neuroinflammation and neuropathic pain. P2X7Rs, predominantly expressed in microglia, mediate ATP-driven $IL-1\beta$ release, contributing to neuroinflammatory diseases. In cultured rat microglia, cilnidipine suppressed P2X7R-mediated calcium influx and $IL-1\beta$ release. In a rat neuropathic pain model, intrathecal cilnidipine reversed nerve injury-induced mechanical hypersensitivity, highlighting its therapeutic potential [13]. Also, Kumar N conducted a study investigating the protective effects of cilnidipine

and nimodipine on stress-induced behavioral changes and memory deficits in mice. Stress increased corticosterone levels, reduced locomotor activity, head dips, rearings, and social interactions, and caused memory deficits. Treatment with cilnidipine (10 mg/kg) and nimodipine (10 mg/kg) significantly alleviated these effects, normalizing both behavioral and memory impairments as well as corticosterone levels. These findings suggest that the calcium channel blockade (L and N-type) by cilnidipine and nimodipine helps mitigate HPA-axis-mediated stress responses, improving behavior and memory under acute stress [14].

Further studies conducted on Cilnidipine by Sternlicht A et al, demonstrated potent inhibition of Nav1.7, showing six times greater efficacy at a 20 mg dose compared to 1800 mg of gabapentin. Research by Lipscombe indicates that N-channel antagonists like cilnidipine may be particularly effective in peripheral pain conditions and thermal hyperalgesia. Currently, under development for treating Raynaud's symptoms in systemic sclerosis, cilnidipine may also hold promise for other peripheral neuropathic pain conditions [15].

Conclusion

Our study concludes that Cilnidipine along with Tramadol shows an additional analgesic effect when compared to control, Tramadol alone, and Tramadol in combination with Amlodipine. Because of the above-mentioned properties, Cilnidipine can be preferred in elderly patients who are suffering from hypertension along with neuropathic pain, which can reduce multidrug exposure and increase patient compliance. Also, it was found that cilnidipine has other stress relief effects, and further exploratory studies are required to confirm them.

References

1. Sharma S, Khare S, Dubey BK, Joshi A, Jain A, Analgesic activity of poly herbal formulation in experimental rats by acetic acid induced writhing test model and Hot plate model, Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics. 2019; 9(2-s):276-280
2. Vickers MD, O' Flaherty D, Szekely SM, ReadM, Yoshizumi J. Tramadol: Pain relief by an opioid without depression of respiration. Anaesthesia. 47(4), 1992, 291-6.
3. Furukawa T, Nukada T, Suzuki K, Fujita Y, Mori Y, Nishimura M and Yamanaka M (1997) Voltage and pH dependent block of cloned N-type $Ca_{v}2.1$ channels by amlodipine. Br J Pharmacol 121, 1136–1140
4. Zhou X, Ono H, Ono Y, Frohlich ED. N- and L- type calcium channel antagonist improve glomerular dynamics, reserves severe nephrosclerosis and inhibits apoptosis and prolifera-

- tion in an L-NAME/SHR model. *J Hypertens* 2002; 20:993-1000.
5. TAKAHARA A, KONDA T, ENOMOTO A, and KONDO N Neuroprotective Effects of a Dual L/N-type Ca²⁺ Channel Blocker Cilnidipine in the Rat Focal Brain Ischemia Model *Biol. Pharm. Bull.* 2004; 27(9) 1388—1391.
 6. K Saha K, Agrawal R, Mohapatra S Amlodipine Potentiates Antinociceptive Activity of Ketorolac and Tramadol – An Experimental Study *IJRPP* 2016; 5(2): 184-191.
 7. Shetty K , Shetty R , Bairy L , Rao P , Kiran A , Shetty M , Deepak , Vidya Nayak V, A Comparative Study on Clinical and Biochemical Parameters in Amlodipine and Cilnidipine Treated Hypertensive Patients, *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*; May 2017;11(5): FC01-FC05.
 8. Pokale A, Murarkar S, Gothankar J, Deshmukh R, Gupta V. Prevalence of hypertension and associated risk factors in urban slums: A community-based cross-sectional study in India. *Indian J Public Health.* 2023; 67(3):474. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijph.ijph_1636_22.
 9. Chatterjee K, Al-Ani M, Loza-Blanco E, Benhamida J, Sinan T, Nawaz A, et al. Cardiovascular risk factors in rheumatoid arthritis: A cross-sectional study. *Cureus.* 2022; 14(8). doi:10.7759/cureus.28088.
 10. Sharma HL, Sharma KK, Pradeep N, Vijaya C. Evaluation of antinociceptive activity of tramadol and its interaction with aspirin and caffeine in mice. *Indian J Pharmacol.* 2013; 45(2):139–43. doi:10.4103/0253-7613.108290.
 11. Murakami M, Nakagawasai O, Fujii S, Hosono M, Hozumi S, Esashi A, et al. Antinociceptive effect of cilnidipine, a novel N-type calcium channel antagonist. *Brain Res.* 2000; 868(1):123-127.
 12. Modi H, Mazumdar B, Bhatt J. Study of interaction of tramadol with amlodipine in mice. *Indian J Pharmacol.* 2013; 45(1):76-79. doi: 10.4103/0253-7613.106440.
 13. Yamashita, T., Kamikaseda, S., Tanaka, A., Tozaki-Saitoh, H., Caaveiro, J. M. M., Inoue, K., & Tsuda, M. (2021). New Inhibitory Effects of Cilnidipine on Microglial P2X7 Receptors and IL-1 β Release: An Involvement in its Alleviating Effect on Neuropathic Pain. *Cells*, 10(2), 434. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells10020434>
 14. Kumar, N., Singh, N., & Jaggi, A. S. (2011). Anti-stress effects of cilnidipine and nimodipine in immobilization subjected mice. *Physiology & Behavior*, 105(5), 1148–1155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2011.12.011>
 15. Sternlicht, A. (2023). Cilnidipine, a novel N-Type specific calcium channel antagonist, has potent activity at the NAV1.7 sodium channel, which may have implications for treatment of certain neuropathic pain conditions (S23.003). *Neurology*, 100(17_supplement_2). <https://doi.org/10.1212/wnl.0000000000203542>